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THE IMPORTANCE OF IN-DEPTH TEACHING OF MATRIX ALGEBRA IN FORMING ANALYTICAL THINKING

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Abstract: This article examines the methodological and practical challenges of teaching matrix algebra as a component of applied mathematics in economics education. It demonstrates the fundamental role of matrix theory in static and dynamic modeling of economic systems, particularly in Leontief's input-output problems, Markov chains, multivariate regression analysis, and linear programming. The article proposes pedagogical strategies aimed at strengthening the cognitive connection between mathematical abstraction and economic interpretation.

Key words: linear algebra, matrix operator, economic modeling, V. Leontief model, endogenous and exogenous variables, Markov processes, multivariate econometrics, economic knowledge.

INTRODUCTION. The modern economy has become a significantly mathematized and formalized system. The complexity of economic processes, their multifactorial and stochastic nature, require a high level of mathematical and abstract thinking from future economists. Teaching linear algebra, particularly matrix theory, in economics courses at higher education levels should not be limited to developing computational skills. Matrices are a fundamental mathematical language describing multidimensional economic space and the contours of global equilibrium within it. However, in teaching practice, a common problem is students mechanically performing matrix operations (multiplication, determinant, inverse matrix) but failing to understand their economic content (cognitive essence). Therefore, it is imperative to fundamentally and practically revise the teaching methods for this section. From a mathematical perspective, a matrix is a linear operator. In economic systems, this operator is a transformation mechanism that transforms the space of resources (INPUT) into the space of products (OUTPUT). If $X \in R^n$ is a vector of production factors, and $Y \in R^n$ is a vector of finished goods, then the relationship between them is defined by an equation with the operator $Y = AX$. Here, $A_{m \times n}$ is a technological matrix indicating the structural efficiency of the system. It is advisable to explain to the student that a matrix is not simply a table of numbers, but an operator encoding the internal structure of an economic system.

Students perform operations on matrices (multiplication, finding the determinant, calculating the inverse matrix) mechanically and algorithmically, but there is a problem of not understanding their cognitive essence and economic content. This

leads to the inability of graduates to use mathematical models in real economic analysis processes. Therefore, it is urgent to fundamentally and practically revise the methodology of teaching this department.

METHODS. For a more in-depth analysis of the classical input-output model $X = \frac{Y}{I-A}$, it is necessary to introduce the properties of square matrices into the educational process. Students learn to assess the viability of a macroeconomic system using mathematical approximations.

Matrices play an important role in economic forecasting. When modeling changes in market shares or consumer behavior, stochastic matrices are used, whose elements consist of probabilities, and the sum of their rows is equal to 1. If P is a matrix of transition probabilities, then the state of the system after period t will be $S(t) = S(0) \cdot P^t$. The significant effectiveness of matrix ranking in economic forecasting is clearly demonstrated here.

Today, the educational process in higher education institutions in the republic has been completely converted to a credit-modular system and is managed using the HEMIS information system. This system prioritizes student independent learning.

When teaching matrix algebra, it is necessary to abandon the rigid curriculum and transform independent study hours into a project-based learning format. To achieve this, students are given the following three-stage independent assignment (case) through their personal account on the HEMIS platform:

Stage One (Collection of Economic Data): The student compiles a small-scale technological matrix A based on 3-4 types of products from a real industry (e.g., light industry, banking, or small business) and the cost of the raw materials consumed.

Stage Two (Mathematical Calculation): The process of determining the inverse matrix or solving a system of linear equations is performed using MS Excel or Python.

Stage Three (Economic Interpretation and Presentation in HEMIS): The student interprets the obtained mathematical result economically and uploads the PDF report to HEMIS for evaluation.

The study was conducted among 120 first-year students studying economics in the 2025/2026 academic year.

Students were divided into two groups:

Control group n=60: Taught using the traditional method (lecture, manual calculations on the board).

Experimental group n=60: Taught using digital tools and the HEMIS platform using the project-based learning (PBL) methodology. 3-stage independent learning model through HEMIS. The following three-stage case assignment was given to the students of the experimental group as an independent work through the HEMIS system:
Collection of economic data: The student constructed a small-scale technological A matrix based on 3-4 product types and raw material costs of a real enterprise.
Mathematical calculation: Determined the inverse of square matrices and solved the model using MS Excel or Python (Numpy library).
Economic interpretation:

Interpreted the obtained mathematical result economically and uploaded the PDF report to the HEMIS system.

RESULTS. At the end of the experiment, students from both groups took a control exam. The exam tasks were divided into two parts: purely mathematical calculations and economic interpretation (interpretation) of the results obtained.

Exam results of the control and experimental groups (on a 100-point scale)

Evaluation criteria	Control group (Mean score)	Experimental group (Average score)	Growth rate (%)
Pure mathematical calculation skills	72,4	81,2	+12,1%
Economic interpretation (Analysis)	48.3	69.5	+43.9%
Overall average achievement	60.35	75.35	+24.8%

The results show that, due to the transition from manual calculations to digital programs, the students in the experimental group were free from technical errors and their calculation skills increased by 12.1%.

The biggest difference was observed in the analytical part: while the students in the traditional group scored an average of 48.3 points due to their inability to relate the matrix to economic models, the students in the project-based methodology scored 69.5 points, which is 43.9% higher. The overall mastery index increased by 24.8%.

This methodological approach serves to purposefully distribute hours of independent work on the subject and develop student skills in independent analysis.

To improve the quality of mathematical education, the structure of lectures and practical classes should be based on the following didactic principles:

Every mathematical theorem and operation should have an economic analog. For example, the color of a matrix reflects the degree of mutual independence of sectors in a system; Cramer's rule or inverse matrices is a method for finding local equilibrium points in an economic system.

Instead of wasting time manually calculating determinants and higher-order matrices, students should be taught to work in digital software systems. In this case, the emphasis is on the economic explanation (interpretation) of the output data. It would be advisable to introduce a system of joint exchanges between economists and mathematics teachers on the topic of input-output balance based on practical examples, such as the industry forecast of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION. In-depth study of matrix algebra in economics education is not simply a requirement of the academic program, but a methodological foundation that shapes the analytical thinking of future economists. Matrix methods allow students to view the economy not as a set of local elements, but as a holistic, structural, and dynamic system. The educational process includes both conceptual and practical aspects.

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